

THE ROLE OF WOMEN & GIRLS IN THE ERA OF DIGITALIZATION: CHALLENGES & OPPORTUNITIES

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Annotation: This article attempts to consider the role of women's and girls, facing challenges in the era of digital technologies. A lack of women working in technology results in under-representation and exclusion in specific areas, such as AI, where a lack of diversity can lead to gender bias. The Internet can cultivate ideology and affect gender norms through its educational and informative functions, where the technology can play a significant role in enhancing women's agency by building digital skills, promoting financial inclusion, and increasing access to information.

Keywords: challenges, opportunities, digitalization, technology, women, education, gender, inequality, role.

РОЛЬ ЖЕНЩИН И ДЕВОЧЕК В ЭРУ ЦИФРОВИЗАЦИИ: ВЫЗОВЫ И ВОЗМОЖНОСТИ

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Аннотация: В данной статье предпринята попытка рассмотреть роль женщин и девочек, сталкивающихся с проблемами в эпоху цифровых технологий. Малое количество женщин, работающих в сфере технологий, приводят к недостаточному представлению женщин, например, об искусственном интеллекте, что может привести к гендерной предвзятости. Интернет может повлиять на гендерные нормы, посредством своих образовательных и информационных функций, где технологии могут сыграть значительную роль в расширении женской активности, путем развития цифровых навыков, содействуя финансовой доступности и расширению доступа к информации.

Ключевые слова: проблемы, возможности, цифровизация, технология, женщины. Образование, гендер, неравенство, роль.

INTRODUCTION

Women and girls often face limited access to education and professional training in technology-related fields. Bridging this gap is crucial for their active participation in the digital economy¹. Traditional gender norms can hinder women's full inclusion in the industrial sector, including digital roles.

OPPORTUNITIES

Access and Education: Women and girls often face limited access to education and professional training in technology-related fields. Bridging this gap is crucial for their active participation in the digital economy¹.

Gender-Based Discrimination: Digital gender-based violence, harassment, and discrimination persist, affecting women's activism and engagement online¹. According, to Charles Kenny and Megan O'Donnel: "Expanding Women's role in Developing Technology, increasing productivity, improving lives" there is a drop off between education & professional research careers &

patenting (particularly in private sector). In engineering, women account for 20 percent of paper authorship in universities & governmental institutes, but only 13 percent in industry.

Societal Norms: Traditional gender norms can hinder women's full inclusion in the industrial sector, including digital roles.

Empowerment through Education: Technical education and economic empowerment can lead to significant gains in human development and well-being for women and society as a whole.

Industry 4.0: The advancement of Industry 4.0 (digitalization in manufacturing) creates opportunities for women in

technical and engineering disciplines. New job profiles, such as data analysts, emerge, offering women more intelligent roles².

CHALLENGES

Pay Gap: Women typically earn less than men for comparable work. In the United States, Hispanic women earned 57.5 cents for every dollar in 2022, while Black women made 69.1 cents¹.

Education Access: Girls are more likely to be out of school, especially in low-income countries. Conflict exacerbates this gap, impacting economic opportunities and safety¹².

Violence: Women and girls are more likely to be murdered by people they know. Family members or intimate partners commit around 55% of female homicides¹.

Sexual Violence: The threat of sexual violence persists for many women. Around 26% of women aged 15 and older have endured intimate partner violence¹.

Unpaid Work: Women disproportionately perform unpaid domestic work, including cooking and caregiving¹.

STEM and Caretaker Jobs: STEM jobs and caretaker roles remain gendered, limiting opportunities for women¹.

Gender inequality is everywhere. According to the World Economic Forum, it could take another 131 years to achieve global gender parity. Inequality affects the treatment, rights and opportunities of women, girls and transgender and gender-diverse people the most, but everyone deals with negative effects. Crises like war, climate change and pandemics can make things worse. How does gender inequality manifest in everyday life? Here are 15 examples:

Women make less money than men

The pay gap is one of the most consequential examples of everyday gender inequality. According to the UN, women make only 77 cents for every dollar men earn, even when they do comparable work. The gap widens for women who have children. Country specifics also reveal racial inequalities. In the United States, Hispanic women earned 57.5 cents for every dollar in 2022, while Black women made 69.1 cents. The Institute for Women's Policy Research estimates that if progress doesn't speed up, it could take 30 years for the US to reach pay equity.

Girls are more likely to be out of school

Education access has improved over the years, but large gaps are still an issue. According to the World Bank, 88% of girls are enrolled in primary school on a global level, but 78% are enrolled in low-income countries. The gap widens in secondary school; only 31% of girls are enrolled in low-income countries compared to the 66% global average. Conflict plays a big role. Girls are 2.5 times more likely than boys to leave school during crises, which impacts their economic opportunities, safety, health and more.

Women and girls are more likely to be murdered by people they know

While men are overall more likely to be murdered, women and girls are more likely to be killed by people they know. Family members or intimate partners commit around 55% of female homicides. That means every hour, more than five women or girls are murdered by someone in their family. Because it's much harder to avoid violent family members or partners, everyday life for women and girls can be dangerous.

Women and girls experience more sexual violence

For many women and girls, the threat of sexual violence is persistent. According to UN Women, 26% of women 15 years and older have endured intimate partner violence, which means their abuser is a romantic and/or sexual partner. Around 15 million girls 15-19 years old have experienced forced sex at some point. Men experience sexual violence, too; according to stats from the United States, around 24.8% of men have experienced unwanted sexual contact. The numbers show it's much more common for women and girls.

Women do more unpaid work

Life is more than paid work and play; people must cook, clean, do laundry, care for children and more. Women do most of this unpaid labor. According to Oxfam, the world's women and girls complete more than ¾ of all unpaid work. That accounts for 12.5 billion hours of unpaid work every day. It's worse for rural women from low-income countries. They can spend up to 14 hours a day doing unpaid care work. This limits their educational and economic opportunities. Gender inequality can manifest in subtle ways. When I was in high school, the girls noticed that one of the male teachers only seemed to call on boys. We started an informal experiment where we raised our hands for every question. More times than not, he would always call on a boy if they had their hands up, too. While we could never prove he was sexist, we felt invisible and undervalued.

Women cook more

Let's look closer at one example of unpaid work: cooking. It's an everyday task that takes significant planning, energy and time. According to one survey, women cook more meals than men in almost every country. In 2022, that totaled a little less than nine meals a week. Men cooked four meals a week. In places like Ethiopia, Egypt, Yemen and Nepal, women cooked eight more meals than men. Italy was the only place where men cooked more than women. The reasons vary, but cooking is typically considered a domestic and "feminine" job. Because of this stereotype, women end up saddled with extra unpaid work.

Discrimination affects gender-diverse and transgender people more than their cisgender counterparts

Gender-diverse and transgender people don't identify with the sex they were assigned at birth and/or traditional gender binaries. Gender inequality affects them, too. Discrimination extends into every area of life, including employment, housing and healthcare. According to the Human Rights Campaign, discrimination disproportionately affects young trans women of color.

Women are sexually harassed at work more often

Work should be a safe place for everyone, but women deal with more sexual harassment. According to the International Labour Organization, young women are twice as likely as young men to experience sexual violence and harassment at work. Migrant women are especially vulnerable; they're twice as likely as non-migrant women to report harassment. Not every industry is the same. According to the Center for American Progress, women who work in male-dominated fields, like warehousing and construction, are most likely to report harassment.

Most people who experience harassment never report it, however, so harassment is happening a lot more often than we know.

STEM jobs are gendered

The STEM field, which stands for science, technology, engineering and math, has been male-dominated for many years. Gender stereotyping is one of the main reasons why. Historically, most societies didn't believe women were fit for these types of jobs. The consequences are still with us today. According to research from LinkedIn, women fill only 3 out

Entrepreneurship and E-Commerce: Digital platforms enable women to start and manage businesses online. E-commerce, social media, and digital marketing provide avenues for female entrepreneurs to reach global audiences.

Remote Work and Flexibility: The rise of remote work allows women to balance professional and personal responsibilities.

STEM Careers: Efforts to encourage women in science, technology, engineering, and mathematics (STEM) fields are paying off. More women are pursuing careers in data science, software development, and cybersecurity.

According to Sreberny ,A "Citizen movement & political struggles for democracy & rights in the region didn't begin with Arab spring and neither did women's political activity. Yet it is reasonable to suggest that access to the Internet have produced a more conducive political activity.

Women in Leadership Roles: Digitalization promotes transparency and inclusivity. Women can leverage their skills to lead in tech companies, startups, and organizations.

Access to Information and Services: Digital platforms provide information on health, education, and legal rights. Women can access resources and support networks online.

In summary, embracing digitalization can empower women, enhance their economic prospects, and contribute to a more equitable society.

Empowering women and girls in digitalization and Industry 4.0 is essential for achieving gender equality and maximizing the potential of the digital revolution.

Адабиётлар руйхати:

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